

Vernal Conjunctivitis

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Clinical Image

A 16-year-old man presented for consultation for second opinion for diagnosis of polyps in tarsal eyelid. Personal history of seasonal conjunctivitis and treatment with topical Tobramycin and Dexamethasone. Visual acuity is 20/20 in both eyes. On ophthalmologic examination, enormous papillae are observed in lower and upper tarsus (arrows) and conjunctival hyperemia (Figure 1). Rest of anterior segment and fundus examination are normal. Patient was diagnosed with vernal conjunctivitis, a type of allergic conjunctivitis, more common in children during spring and fall months. Symptoms are: itching, photophobia and tearing. Most important clinical sign is large papillae and adherent mucous secretion.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

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Figure 1: